

Skeptical Bayesian Priors and Second-Generation p -Values

Ben G. Fitzpatrick^{1,2}

¹Loyola Marymount University, 1 LMU Drive, Los Angeles, CA 90045

²Tempest Technologies, 7973 W. 83rd Street, Playa del Rey, CA 90293

Abstract

Second-generation p -values (SGPVs) offer a simple means of assessing hypothesis tests. They also improve upon traditional p -values in important ways, especially in the introduction of an interval null hypothesis. Roughly speaking, the amount of overlap of this interval with a confidence interval derived from data determines the SGPV. A seemingly very different approach to hypothesis testing uses a skeptical prior in a Bayesian setting. Relating the spread of the skeptical prior to the interval null, we compare posterior probabilities to SGPVs. We examine these two approaches for some common hypothesis testing problems that arise in biological research, such as simple two-group comparisons, ANOVAs

Key Words: Bayesian inference, second-generation p -value, hypothesis testing

1. Introduction

Fisher's recommendation for p -value thresholding at the 0.05 level has deeply penetrated most empirical life and social science research. The process of science now depends heavily on statistical inference, especially the p -value. Diggle and Chetwynd (2011) suggest that scientific theories can only be falsified and not proven and that "the inferential character of statistical method is in complete harmony with this view of science." Other statisticians take issue with null hypothesis statistical testing (NHST) as falsification (see, e.g., McElreath, 2020). Indeed, as evidenced in a 2019 volume of *The American Statistician* (see Wasserstein, Schirm, and Lazar, 2019, for an overview) dedicated to statistical inference, there is no clear alternative to the p -value. Even if there were, the transition away from p -values appears quite problematic (Goodman, 2019).

A recent innovation to ease that transition is the second-generation p -value (SGPV) of Blume *et al* (2019). The SGPV is used to test a null interval hypothesis, such as $H_0: -\varepsilon < \theta < \varepsilon$, rather than the traditional point null of $H_0: \theta = 0$. In this framework, the null quantifies a level of scientific significance. The SGPV, like the traditional p -value, is a number on the probability scale of 0 to 1, but what it represents is a degree of compatibility of the data with the null hypothesis.

One different route to replacing the p -value is that of Bayesian inference (McElreath, 2020). When considering interval null hypotheses, one can directly compute the posterior probability of the null hypothesis without the difficulty of mixing discrete and continuous prior models. Choosing a prior distribution is in general a challenge, but one approach that aligns with the process of NHST is skepticism. With an interval null, we can concentrate prior probability around the null hypothesis and allowing the data to "move the needle" from skepticism to evidentiary strength of a positive finding.

In this note, we compare the SGPV with a skeptical Bayesian approach to interval NHST. Section 2 discusses the basic models of both approaches, and Section 3 illustrates them with some simple examples. Section 4 wraps up with some observations and potential future inquiries.

2. Second Generation p -Values and Skeptical Bayesian Hypothesis Tests

2.1 Introduction to Second Generation p -Values

The SGPV is really a very straightforward idea. The only statistical model it requires is a confidence interval I around an estimator $\hat{\theta}$ for a parameter whose value is subject to the NHST. The hypothesis test of interest is $H_0: -\varepsilon < \theta < \varepsilon$, and the null interval is denoted $J = (-\varepsilon, \varepsilon)$. The overlap of these two intervals leads to the SGPV:

$$p_\varepsilon = \frac{|I \cap J|}{|I|} \max \left\{ 1, \frac{|I|}{2|J|} \right\},$$

in which $|*|$ denotes interval length. Blume *et al* (2019) are careful to point out that any sort of confidence interval can be used: parametric, nonparametric, or even a Bayesian credible interval. The confidence interval is the sole model of the data in this approach. Roughly speaking, the relative amount of overlap between the confidence interval and the null interval determines the SGPV.

The second factor in the definition importantly acts as a correction factor for small sample sizes: when I is large relative to J , the denominator becomes $2|J|$ instead of $|J|$. Without this correction, the SGPV could be small even when the confidence interval contains the null interval. Consider the situation of $I = (-100\varepsilon, 100\varepsilon)$ – here, without the correction factor, $p_\varepsilon = 0.01$! With the correction, $p_\varepsilon = 0.5$, which is the maximum value of the SGPV when the confidence interval is larger than twice the null interval.

As opposed to the standard p -value, the SGPV can be interpreted as a measure of hypothesis-data compatibility, with large overlap viewed as supporting the null hypothesis and small overlap supporting the alternative (Blume *et al*, 2019).

When the confidence interval is small enough relative to the null interval, the SGPV can be viewed as the likelihood that a random point in the confidence interval is in the null interval, and as such represents a type of posterior probability of the null.

Figure 1: Comparing null interval and confidence interval for SGPV computation.

2.2 Bayesian Hypothesis Testing: SGPV and Skepticism

Figure 1 suggests a Bayesian interpretation of the SGPV is possible. One can take this a step further by considering a uniform (improper) prior. In that case, the likelihood function becomes the posterior. Next, we make a very coarse approximation of that posterior, with a uniform distribution concentrated on the confidence interval. In this situation, the SGPV is an approximation of the posterior probability of the null.

More generally, the computation of the null posterior probability is given by

$$\Pr[J | y] = \int_{-\varepsilon}^{\varepsilon} \pi(\theta | y) d\theta,$$

in which $\pi(\theta|y)$ denotes the posterior distribution. While the Bayes factor (Jeffreys, 1961) alternative to NHST is more common, the posterior probability of the null interval compares in an interesting way to the SGPV. The posterior acts as a more general weighting on the null interval, as opposed to the “0-1” weighting that the confidence interval applies.

Of course, the computation of the null interval’s posterior probability requires a prior and a likelihood function, the latter being a natural (but not necessary in nonparametric approaches) component of the SGPV’s confidence interval. We denote the likelihood by $f(y|\theta)$. For the prior, we begin with a probability density π^* with central value (mean or median, depending on the application) of 0 and an appropriate unit of scale. We then scale this density to create a skeptical prior:

$$\pi_0(\theta) = \frac{1}{\varepsilon} \pi\left(\frac{\theta}{\varepsilon}\right).$$

We call this prior skeptical because it concentrates the prior probability on the null interval, for a *priori* thinking that the alternative is at least somewhat unlikely.

For a normal prior,

$$\pi(\theta) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2\pi\tau^2}} \exp\left\{-\frac{\theta^2}{2\tau^2}\right\}$$

we see different levels of skepticism in Figure 2.

Figure 2: Levels of skepticism concerning the null interval, represented by priors with different variance.

3. Examples

3.1 Normal data with known variance

As a first example, one in which all of the computations can be performed without simulation, we consider the problem of estimating a normal mean when the variance is known. In particular, we take independent and identically distributed normal data with unknown mean, θ , and known variance of 1. As above, we use the interval null hypothesis is $H_0: -\varepsilon < \theta < \varepsilon$. The sample average estimator $\hat{\theta} = \left(\frac{1}{n}\right) \sum y_i$ has a 95% confidence interval of $\hat{\theta} \pm 1.96/\sqrt{n}$, so that

$$|I| = \frac{3.92}{\sqrt{n}},$$

$$|J| = 2\varepsilon,$$

$$|I \cap J| = \max\{0, (\min\{\varepsilon, \hat{\theta} + 1.96/\sqrt{n}\} - \max\{-\varepsilon, \hat{\theta} - 1.96/\sqrt{n}\})\}.$$

This information gives us the necessary components of the SGPV computation.

For the Bayesian approach, we choose a normal prior $\pi_0(\theta) \sim N(0, (\tau = k\varepsilon)^2)$ in which k is a (scale) design parameter. The posterior is then

$$\pi(\theta|y) \sim N\left(\frac{n}{\frac{1}{(k\varepsilon)^2} + n} \hat{\theta}, \left(\frac{1}{\frac{1}{(k\varepsilon)^2} + n}\right)^{-1}\right).$$

Our first comparison is of three quantities: the p -value, the SGPV, and the null interval posterior probability (NPP), all computed as functions of the observed mean value (or effect size). Figures 3 and 4 illustrate these quantities for two different parameter specifications.

Figure 3. Comparison of the p -value, the SGPV, and null interval posterior probability as a function of the observed “effect” $\hat{\theta}$ for $\varepsilon = 0.5, k = 2, n = 16$.

Figure 4. Comparison of the p -value, the SGPV, and null interval posterior probability as a function of the observed “effect” $\hat{\theta}$ for $\varepsilon = 0.5, k = 2, n = 2$.

The level of skepticism here is perhaps not so great: the prior probability of the null interval is a little over 38% when the prior standard deviation is twice the value of ε . Were we to set prior $\Pr[J] = 0.75$, the null posterior probability increases, making it more difficult to reject H_0 , as shown in Figure 5.

Figure 5. Comparison of the p -value, the SGPV, and null interval posterior probability as a function of the observed “effect” $\hat{\theta}$ for $\varepsilon = 0.5, k = 0.86, n = 16$. Here k is chosen to achieve 75% prior probability of the null interval.

In another comparison, we look at these three quantities as functions of both the observed effect and the data’s standard deviation (assuming $n = 1$ but σ varies). Figure 6 contains heat maps illustrating this comparison.

Figure 6. Comparison of the p -value, the SGPV, and null interval posterior probability as a function of the observed “effect” $\hat{\theta}$ and the data standard deviation σ . the black curves show the 0.05 threshold for rejecting the null.

4. Discussion

In this paper we explored the recent inferential innovation that is the second-generation p -value. This quantity is extremely simple to compute, making it a promising alternative to traditional p -values. Moreover, it has an interpretation as an approximate posterior probability of the null. While a fully Bayesian posterior probability computation provides more flexibility, the two computations compare reasonably well in the simple examples we have presented. In future work we plan to look at more realistic and complex inference problems that arise in biomedical, biological, and social science research.

References

- Blume, J., Greevy, R., Welty, V., Smith, J., and DuPont, W. (2019), "An Introduction to Second Generation p-Value," *The American Statistician*, **73** No S1, 157-167.
- Diggle, P.J., and A. G. Chetwynd (2011), *Statistics and Scientific Method*, Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- Goodman, S. (2019), "Why is Getting Rid of p-Values So Hard? Musings on Science and Statistics," *The American Statistician*, **73**, No. S1, 26–30.
- Jeffreys, H. (1961), *Theory of Probability* (3rd ed). Oxford: Oxford University Press.
- McElreath, R. (2020), *Statistical Rethinking*, Boca Raton: CRC Press.
- Wasserstein, R.L., A.L. Schirm, N. A. Lazar (2019), "Moving to a World Beyond 'p<0.05,'" *The American Statistician*, **73**, No. S1, 1-19.